

MONITORING AND CONTROL OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES IN FOOD PRODUCING ANIMALS

Initiative towards a strategic research agenda on **Monitoring and control of infectious diseases in food-producing animals**

Towards

Sustainable production of safe food from healthy animals

by improved

Monitoring and control of infectious diseases in food producing animals

This document is an invitation to contribute to a strategic research agenda towards competitive and sustainable livestock production by improved monitoring and control of infectious diseases in food producing animals.

Better monitoring and control of infectious diseases in food producing animals is essential for a more sustainable way of production of safe food from healthy animals.

Support of this strategic research will contribute to the realization of the sustainable development goals (SDG): building public-private-partnerships (SDG17) to boost innovation (SDG9) supply of nutritious, safe and healthy food (SDG 2), reducing environmental impact, making better use of resources (SDG 12), respecting animal welfare and safeguarding human and animal (SDG 3) and environment (SDG 13 & 15) health thus responding to the requirements of the consumer/citizen.

These goals can best be achieved through a concerted action between academia, industry and the primary sector and through a research agenda that is aligned with priorities set by STAR-IDAZ IRC, gaps identified by DISCONTTOOLS and with broader initiatives supporting sustainable livestock production (e.g. ATF) in Europe. To boost innovation the European research infrastructure is of imminent importance for joining forces with industry's R&D capabilities and capacities. The private and the public structures are intensively linked for cooperation and cross-pollination, both in the precompetitive and the competitive area. Europe's strong research infrastructure should be maintained as Centre of Excellence, for biological sciences, socio-economic and environmental sciences.

Said strategic research agenda can result from intensive and coordinated interaction and discussion between academia and industry both at regional/national and at international/European level.

Entrepreneurial universities can play an important role in facilitating the route to market of new technologies and innovations and in the generation of ecosystems where researchers, innovators, industries and governments join forces to adopt a mission oriented and impact-focused approach to the challenges livestock production is facing.

The increasing need for healthy and safe animal protein – aspects of One Health

The need for sustainable production of sufficient and safe animal protein to feed the growing world population is increasing fast. It is estimated that the world population will increase from 7 to more than 9 billion by 2050. Food supply must therefore increase with 70% by 2050. The growth of the middle class, mainly in developing and BRIC-countries, will increase the demand for high-quality animal

protein and lead to a greater demand for livestock production. An increase in meat production from 218 million ton in 2000 to 376 million ton in 2030 is expected. To take part to this evolution, livestock production in Europe should be sustainable and competitive at a global level.

For both aspects, optimal animal health and welfare is essential as it contributes to efficient growth and minimal output of waste and (antimicrobial) residues in the environment. Research on animal welfare provides knowledge on welfare hazards, their consequences and on potential indicators/biomarkers of welfare. It thus contributes to innovation in the development of tools and methodologies for identifying more welfare-friendly methods, procedures or practices as well as to monitor their effect on welfare.

Zoonoses deserve special attention (One Health context). About 60% of all pathogens that threaten humans originate from animals which is illustrated again by the COVID-19 crisis. It is therefore important for public health that we limit the spread of these zoonotic pathogens. Innovative new products that are beneficial for society, for example by reducing the public health risks posed by certain zoonotic diseases, can have an immense benefit to society, but often have limited or no benefit for the animal. Given the challenges that are faced by society to ensure an affordable supply of safe food from animals, while limiting the risks to public health, a route to market for such products needs to be laid out.

Related to food safety we want to pay special attention to enteric pathogens. The last decade, a group of gastro-intestinal diseases have emerged in animals and are still increasing in prevalence. Strikingly, such trends are occurring simultaneously in human and animal health (One Health). Said diseases include chronic inflammatory diseases and undefined enteritis syndromes, and diseases caused by pathogenic micro-organisms. Specific attention should go to bacteria related to food safety like Salmonella and Campylobacter. Said pathogens colonize the gut of production animals, contaminate animal products and are thus easily transmitted to humans. Also here, gaps identified by DISCONTTOOLS should be considered when defining the research agenda.

Innovation in animal health can be stimulated by cross pollination between the animal and human health sector which is possible for various technologies like drugs (eg alternatives to antibiotics), medtech, big data and many others. Depending on the technology, the product (drug, diagnostic, wearable, IoT, ...) could be marketed in both sectors (with first validation in animal care) or repurposed to the animal care sector in case of failure in human health. Bioinformatics and biomarker development for diseases transcend species, uniting the biology of disease understanding across the animal kingdom. Solutions for newly emerging infectious diseases in animals may help protect the health of people. One important driver is that the animal care sector is characterized by shorter development phases, lower development cost and lower risk profiles with higher probability of success in achieving marketing authorization when compared to the human care sector.

Challenges and possible solutions for better control of infectious diseases

Optimizing health of food producing animals will only be possible through a better and more intelligent control of infectious diseases, mainly through prevention, in order to avoid huge losses due to outbreaks of infectious diseases or to more chronic subclinical disease complexes.

There are however some complicating factors.

At global level the intensity of livestock production increases leading to larger units/farms, increased transport of animals and the pathogens they carry and increased mixing of different strains of (related)

pathogens within a population of animals. To keep such intensive production sustainable, it is important to minimize major outbreaks of infectious diseases and the associated losses. This can be achieved by appropriate biosecurity measures and by continued monitoring of the health status of the animals and the pathogens that circulate.

Climate change is speeding up the spread of infectious diseases, often through their vectors. This will create new variants of known pathogens with new virulence characteristics. Rapid diagnosis and control will thus be essential to control disease spread and to prevent large losses.

Increasing antibiotic and anthelmintic resistance is another growing threat worldwide. More and more pathogens escape from the activities of these antibiotics/anthelmintics and alternative (preventive) measures should be developed. Vaccines are considered to be one of the main alternatives to antibiotics, but also other solutions that allow the host to defend itself more effectively against the infection (eg immunostimulation, passive immunization / immunotherapy) gain more and more attention. Management systems on farm will combine data from monitoring of (subclinical) infectious diseases with data on biosafety measures and on production and behavior of the animals. Based on the combination of these data thresholds can be defined for more accurate and targeted use of drugs on individual animals (precision livestock farming) or on herd level when needed. Deviations from normal animal health status and normal animal behavior will thus be detected sooner which contributes to improved animal welfare.

An integrated approach

Optimal health and welfare of food-producing animals can only be obtained when a combination of tools is available to the veterinarian/farmer:

- Implementation and monitoring of biosafety to reduce influx of pathogens and their spread within the farm
- rapid and more precise diagnostics and tools for the monitoring of health and infection
- animal friendly and/or non-invasive sampling methods or tools
- novel methods that prevent or cure infection and/or empower the animal's general defense against infection
 - new and improved veterinary vaccines including autogenous vaccines or easily adaptable vaccine platforms
 - new delivery methods causing less stress to animals (e.g. oral delivery of vaccines)
 - new feed additives/drugs
 - use of biomarkers of disease resistance or immunity in breeding programs
- veterinary medicinal products
 - in the framework of AMR
 - optimal dose regimens (depending on MICs)
 - possibilities to have antibiograms in due time (timeframe is important to be as short as possible)
 - Availability of a sufficient number of authorised veterinary medicinal products
- recording of food and water intake, growth rate and production (e.g. milk, eggs)

Excellence in veterinary science, advances in biotechnology and new technologies (such as next generation sequencing, synthetic biology and systems biology) and tools are already available today in Europe but they should be combined in an integrated approach. This offers great opportunities for

coordinated multidisciplinary research and development actions leading to concrete and applicable solutions.

Assuring optimal health of food-producing animals requires intensive monitoring and rapid diagnosis and effective, rapid and preferably preventive, treatment in cases of increased infection pressure. For the latter new routes of vaccine administration for mass vaccination (for example oral vaccines) on farms with increasing size are explored. More general and non-specific support of the immune system of the host could provide another part of the solution.

The development of vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics is always a multidisciplinary project and requires not only the knowledge of the target/antigen/biomarker but a lot of other complementary expertise: adjuvants, formulation, expression systems for recombinant proteins, vectors for vaccine delivery, etc. New technologies such as targeting of antigens via carrier antibodies/nanobodies are also used in vaccine development. Specialized laboratories or small biotech companies/start-ups have further developed these technologies and can be valuable partners.

Data from the monitoring of infectious diseases will be combined on farm with production data and data on behavior of the animals, intake of feed and drinking water (digitisation of livestock production), farm management and disinfection protocols to make optimal decisions on use of preventive or curative measures from a clinical, epidemiological, environmental and economical viewpoint (precision livestock farming).

Socio-economic research will assess how current solutions and future innovations are perceived by society and potential users, identification of technical, economic and emotional/cultural hurdles that prevent optimal uptake, concepts/models to predict uptake and optimize uptake. This enhances the responsible use of veterinary medicines. Assessing the value of prevention, infection control and the human-animal bond should demonstrate the relevance the innovations have for society.

Finally, the layout of a sustainable business model can move the research findings to innovative solutions, accepted and optimally used.

Innovative solutions backed up by solid research and science

While many tools and technologies to optimize monitoring and control of infectious diseases are already available today, more research is essential to take full profit from the new opportunities they offer. Moreover, it is important that the research pipeline is supported along its length: basic research is still needed as this is the basis on which new technologies and innovations for the market are developed.

Basic research is a prerequisite to gain more and better insights into the interactions between pathogens, including zoonoses, and their hosts. Increased understanding of the way the pathogens infect their host, replicate and persist in the host and of the virulence factors that are critical in this process leads to the identification of novel targets on the pathogen or on the host. These targets constitute the basis for the development of new vaccines, therapeutics and/or diagnostics.

Besides a good understanding of specific host-pathogen interactions an understanding of more general aspects of vaccinology, immunology, pharmacology (PK/PD) and progressive insight into new technologies for the production and administration of vaccines, immunotherapeutics and health-promoting supplements is required. Better understanding of immunology at the cellular and molecular level and more attention to non-specific immunity with higher homology between species will allow us to develop more generic technologies and technology platforms. Proper management of the intellectual property that is thus created and further development towards concrete applications will assure that these technologies can be exploited more widely.

Insights into the behavior and distribution of zoonotic diseases in humans and animals can lead to the development of new strategies and technologies that not only provide a solution for animal health, but also can be translated into new applications in humans (translational, One Health).

Most gastro-intestinal diseases and syndromes are exceedingly complex because of the interaction between the host and the microbiota, which can be influenced by environmental and nutritional factors. Indeed, both communication between gastro-intestinal micro-organisms (intra- and inter-species), and between micro-organisms and the host (inter-kingdom) can influence gastro-intestinal health either in a beneficial or a negative way. These interactions can be influenced by nutrition and medication (prophylactic and curative) and the animal's immune and defense mechanisms in order to restore unbalanced host-microbiota interactions. Because of the complexity of the gastric and gut environment, studying the etiology and pathogenesis of gastro-intestinal diseases and the host's immune/defense mechanisms requires an inter-disciplinary approach in which microbiology, molecular biology, veterinary medicine and immunology, nutrition, and many other disciplines are involved. This is of crucial importance when preventive measures against disease and impairment of gastro-intestinal health need to be developed.

Strong consortia can develop innovative solutions

The objectives described above can only be achieved by partnerships between world class academics and industry working on a common strategic research agenda with each party playing at their strengths.

Intensive interaction with the primary sector must assure that the knowledge of the pathogen-host interactions together with the understanding of the pathogenesis and the impact of the infection on animal health and performance provides solutions that can be implemented in practice.

Bringing new diagnostics, therapeutics, vaccines and feed additives to the market also requires knowledge of the regulatory framework (in view of the new legislation, Regulation 2019/6, that will be implemented by January 2022) and the market in which these new technologies have to perform.

The creation of strong consortia and partnerships between academia, industry and the primary sector is thus essential for the development of new and effective strategies to control infectious diseases.

Entrepreneurial universities can play an important role in facilitating the route to market of new technologies and innovations and in the generation of ecosystems where researchers, innovators, industries and governments join forces to adopt a mission oriented and impact-focused approach to the challenges livestock production is facing.

As an example Ghent University, with the support of IOF, has adopted a combination of i) business development clusters as part of the tech transfer organization and ii) access to proof of concept funding (see infographic below) to mature and de-risk innovative technologies. The business development clusters join the insights and know-how of academic scientists who perform breakthrough research with high quality management of the collaboration with industrial partners by an experienced team of tech transfer professionals with special attention to swift contract negotiations, management of intellectual property and follow up of milestones and deliverables. Both elements of the combination, the cluster and the proof of concept projects, have proven to significantly facilitate reaching out to industry and to initiate first collaborations with industrial partners in preparation of a transfer of the technology.

While such organization enables universities to better evaluate the market potential of new technologies and set the first steps towards academic-industrial partnership, this should be complemented with other support and funding schemes at national and EU-level. Co-funding mechanisms with industry, funding bodies at regional/national and EU level, foundations and other sources of funding should thus be promoted, both at EU and national level.

The Partnerships within Horizon Europe are a great example of how said co-funding can be organized and a Partnership Animal Health & Welfare will stimulate collaboration between the different actors in this innovation space. Moreover, such Partnership will encourage concertation with other European initiatives and engagements with the rest of the world (e.g. STAR-IDAZ IRC, EPIZONE, OneHealth EJP [MED-VET-NET](#), [EPIZONE](#), [AFarCloud](#), the [Network of Evaluation of One Health](#), [JPI AMR/JPIAMR VRI](#) and others). International coordination with support of relevant national, regional and European authorities, other European Partnerships and relevant projects would guarantee efficient dissemination of the outcomes, thus ensuring maximum impact.

Coordinated public-public and public-private collaboration by European actors will ensure reduced socio-economic and environmental impact of health and welfare issues, protect the economic viability of farms and provide a source of safer and healthier food, with the ultimate goal of delivering healthy animals for a healthy world.

Said coordinated collaborations allow us to develop proprietary technology towards market-ready products and will have a leveraging effect on the impact of basic research. The partnerships will lead to multidisciplinary consortia that can deliver a major contribution to strategic research agendas at national, European and global level.

The economic importance of monitoring and controlling infectious diseases in livestock

The livestock sector contributes substantially to the European economy:

- €168 billion annually¹
- 45% of the total agricultural activity but much higher in countries like Ireland (74.2%), Denmark (66.4%), UK (60.2%) and Belgium (58.9%)

It creates employment for almost 30 million people. Reduction of livestock farming would affect the vitality of many European territories and the supply of high quality and safe European animal products while favouring imports of animal foods with lower standard quality.

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http://www.animaltaskforce.eu/Portals/0/ATF/Downloads/Facts%20and%20figures%20sustainable%20and%20competitive%20livestock%20sector%20in%20EU_Final.pdf

<https://meatthefacts.eu/home/more-than-meats-the-eye/the-importance-of-livestock/>

The global market for veterinary vaccines was estimated in 2017 at 8059 million USD (7,42 billion EURO) and is expected to grow to 12845 million USD (11,8 billion EURO) in 2025¹.

The market for feed additives was valued at 19642 million USD (18,1 billion EURO) in 2017 and will increase to 31387 million USD (28,9 billion EURO) by 2025 with an important and growing share of the additives with a health supportive effect.²

The veterinary diagnostics market was valued over 3 billion USD (2,76 billion EURO) in 2018 and is expected to witness more than 8% CAGR from 2019 to 2025 and reach a total market value of 5,5 billion USD (5,06 billion EURO).³

¹ <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/animal-vaccines-market>

² <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/animal-feed-additives-market>

³ <https://www.qminsights.com/industry-analysis/animal-diagnostics-market>

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

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